

Preserving Heritage: Traditional Sculpting Techniques of Sukhuapada Village, Odisha

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Abstract

Sukhuapada village in Odisha serves as a living repository of India's rich sculptural heritage, preserving a 1,400-year-old tradition of stone carving. This article investigates the unique practices of the village artisans, who have inherited and perpetuated age-old techniques while adapting to contemporary demands. The research focuses on the meticulous processes that define this traditional craft, offering insights into its historical continuity and cultural significance. A significant aspect of this study is the examination of tools employed in sculpting, tracing their evolution from simple, handcrafted implements of the past to the inclusion of modern tools that complement the craft's traditional roots. By juxtaposing old and new methods, the article reveals how Sukhuapada's sculptors maintain a delicate balance between heritage preservation and innovation. The article also explores the indigenous methods of stone consolidation traditionally used by the artisans. These practices, deeply entrenched in local knowledge systems, ensure the durability and resilience of their creations, exemplifying an enduring commitment to quality and sustainability. Furthermore, the study discusses the ecological wisdom inherent in these techniques, which align seamlessly with modern sustainability principles, offering valuable lessons for contemporary conservation efforts. Through this exploration, the article seeks to highlight the artistic and cultural importance of Sukhuapada's sculpting traditions in the broader context of India's intangible heritage. It underscores the challenges and opportunities in preserving this craft in the face of modernisation and globalisation, advocating for its recognition as a vital cultural treasure. By documenting these practices, this research not only celebrates Sukhuapada's legacy but also contributes to the discourse on safeguarding traditional art forms for future generations.

Keywords: *Sukhuapada village, traditional sculpting techniques, stone carving, indigenous craftsmanship, heritage preservation, sustainable art practices, Odisha sculpture tradition.*

Introduction

Sukhuapada is an ancient village located in Darpana Tehsil, Jajpur District of Odisha. It is located adjacent to an ancient settlement dating back to the post-Mauryan period based on archaeological remains retrieved from nearby areas. Sukhuapada village is situated on the slope of Parabhadi hill; a part of natural hill formation; Nandapahad or Lalitagiri. Lalitagiri is a famous Buddhist settlement of the early historical period with a cultural sequence; Post-Mauryan, Kushan, Gupta, and Bhaumakara periods. The brick and stone structural remains including several fine sculptures of Buddha, Bodhisattva, Tara, Maitreyi etc., defines a wide Buddhism settlement here in early 6th - 7th century C.E. (Patnaik, 2016). Hieun Tsang mentioned about the diamond triangle of Buddhism in his travel itinerary which is identified as the modern-day hillocks, Udayagiri, Ratnagiri, and Lalitagiri of Odisha. All three hillocks have Buddhist settlements with fine members of sculptural art (Mukherjee, 1957).

Sculpting art in Odisha

Odisha is famous for its sculpting art and crafts since historic times. Art is a medium of expression of human cognitive development and skill. Visual forms of art need a certain level of techniques and technology. Such people who create art can be termed as artisans, craftsmen etc., which in other words are called *kalākār*, *śilpi*, *bindhani*, *moharāna*, *kārigar* etc., (Chandra, 2019). Historically we have evidence of different types of artisans and their hierarchy mentioned in manuscripts and traditional texts. The major classifications of traditional artisans in Odisha are, *Sthapati* (architect or chief engineer), *Sutragrahina* (engineer), *Bardhanika* (stone cutters), *Takśaka* (sculptors) (Dey, 2016:184).

Sculptural art in Odisha is world popular for its intricate detailing and emotional aesthetics since historic times. From the Mauryan monolith elephant at Dhauri to the Konark Sun temple, the artistic works have seen its gradual growth and reached zenith due time. The artisans and the craftsmanship behind these marvels and beautiful creations need to be celebrated and promoted more globally to enrich and embrace our incredible and rich cultural heritage. The state's sculpting tradition is deeply rooted in its temple-building culture, with artisans crafting intricate motifs and religious figures that blend spirituality with craftsmanship. These techniques have been passed down for generations, with each artisan contributing to the preservation and evolution of this rich legacy.

Sukhuapada – Craft village

Sukhuapada village is located on the south-eastern and eastern slope of the Parabhadi hill spreading up to the foothill of Olasuni hill. It is covered by the khondalite hills and sparse green vegetation with few ponds around. This village presently consists of approximately 540 families out of which 300 are working on stone carvings and stone sculptural art. Most of these families have been working on stone mediums over generations. They believe that their ancestors were the sculptors of the major monumental architectures of Odisha since the early medieval period and they are following their footsteps and legacy ahead. Even today, several families are associated with the major temples of Odisha and are invited for the annual festivals of Puri Jagannath Dham and Kendrapada Baldev ji mandir etc. This village is under consideration for the 'Crafts Village' scheme proposed by the Union Ministry of Textile in 2018 (The Indian Express, 2022).

Traditional Sculpting Techniques

The sculpting techniques of Sukhuapada are deeply rooted in ancient practices outlined in the *śilpaśāstra*, which serve as manuals for Indian artisans. These texts provide guidelines on proportions, motifs, and the spiritual significance of sculptures, ensuring that each creation adheres to sacred principles.

The process begins with the selection of stone, which is a critical step in ensuring the quality of the final product. Stones such as sandstone, granite, and soapstone are commonly used, each chosen for its specific properties. Once the stone is selected, the artisans sketch the design directly onto the surface using natural pigments.

Three types of major stones are mentioned in Silparatnakosa which are; *Muguni* (black granite), *sahana* (sandstone) and *kuṇḍika* (khondolite) (Mahapatra, 1995). These stones are locally now termed as *muguni* (granite), *kuṇḍa/kaṇḍa* (khondolite), *khadi pathar* (sandstone), *baulamalia* (coloured soft stone), *maṅkada pathara* (laterite) etc.

The artisans of Sukhuapada use different types of stones from different locations for their works based on the requirement and suitability. Majority of the stone works are made from the locally available white spotted Khondalite stones from Parabhadi hills. Apart from that, Khondalite stones are bought from Tapang (Khurda District), Balasore and Mayurbhanj Districts. Green Limestone and Pyrophyllite (soft stone) are acquired from Keonjhar District. Red sandstone is brought from Bansipal area in Rajasthan (Maharana, 2023).

Once the suitable type of stone is selected for a work, the drawing and carving process begins. The carving itself is a meticulous process that involves several stages. The initial rough shaping is done with large chisels and hammers, followed by finer carving with specialised tools. The final stages involve polishing the sculpture to enhance its texture and applying natural oils to protect it from weathering. Each step requires immense skill, patience, and an intimate understanding of the material.

Tools of the Trade: From Ancient Implements to Modern Adaptations

The tools used for stone carving by Sukhuapada's sculptors are a blend of traditional and modern. The traditional tools made of iron based on the time-tested techniques and generational knowledge passed on by their ancestors, are handcrafted by local blacksmiths.

Most of the traditional tools are customised and created as per the necessity and each tool has its own name and significance in the process of carving. The commonly used tools to cut and carve the stones are *tagi*, *guna tagi*, *muna*, *sheni*, *batali*, etc. These can be identified as different types of chisels, mallets and rasps in modern day tools. Further, *sheni* (chisels) has several variations and varieties which are used to chisel different intricate designs. *Gunati sheni*, *dangi sheni*, *muna sheni*, *patuli sheni*, *gunta sheni*, *bambu sheni* etc., (fig.1,2 & 3) are some of them (Maharana, 2023).

Fig.1. *Gunati sheni*

Fig.2. *Gunta sheni* - used in stone cutting.

In recent years, modern tools such as electric drills, grinders, and polishing machines have been introduced and used by the Sukhuapada artisans to upgrade their commercial value and save manual labour time. While these tools increase efficiency and reduce the physical strain on artisans, they are used selectively to ensure that the traditional aesthetic of the sculptures is not compromised. The integration of modern tools has also enabled the artisans to meet the growing demand for their work, particularly in the export market (Mohapatra, 2019). Yet, the traditional integrity of the stone carving is hampered significantly which is seen reflected in certain works. The commercial market and the increase in demand for traditional stone sculptures as a decorative art piece has influenced the local artisans to move towards modern machineries and tools.

Fig.3. Different types of traditional sheni used in stone carvings.

Apart from the available modern chisels and tools, the artisan's custom makes their tools as per their feasibility to use. Some of the modern *sheni* in use are 1 *doriya* diamond *sheni*, 1/2 *doriya* diamond *sheni*, *tarang muna*, *lajji*, *patuli muna* etc (fig.4&5). These can be associated with chisels like, point chisel, flat chisel, diamond chisel, rondel chisel, cross-cut chisel, cape chisel, cow-mouth chisel, round chisel etc.

Fig.4. Modern *sheni* used by the Sukhuapada artisans

Fig.5. Modern chisels – flat, diamond, rondel, crosscut chisel used by the artisans.

Stone Consolidation Methods: Indigenous Practices for Longevity

One of the most remarkable aspects of Sukhuapada's sculpting tradition is the emphasis on stone consolidation. This involves treating the stone to enhance its durability and resistance to environmental factors such as moisture, heat, and pollution.

Traditional methods of stone consolidation include the application of natural oils, such as neem or linseed oil, which penetrate the stone's surface and create a protective layer. In some cases, herbal extracts are used to prevent fungal growth and maintain the stone's texture. These methods not only prolong the life of the sculptures but also reflect the artisans' deep understanding of material science. Apart from prevention, traditional methods are used in conservation and consolidation of stones which is still sparsely practised in Sukhuapada.

A traditional technique of making a natural adhesive is still prevalent in Sukhuapada which is used in consolidating broken stones and fixing them. This natural adhesive paste is made using naturally available herbs, pigments, resins, fruits, and minerals. One such method of making this natural adhesive paste which is still used in Sukhuapada is made using the following ratio and proportion,

Bilva or Bhel – Stone Apple	- 250g
Kendu or Tendu – Indian Persimmon	- 250g
Gud – Jaggery	- 400g
Chuna – Lime	- 250g
Triphala (Amalaki, Bibhitaki, Haritaki)	- 600g
Surkhi – Brick powder	- 100g

These ingredients are put on a large stone trough and mixed well together and soaked in water and let to ferment for a month (fig.6). A thick resin like adhesive (fig.7) is then made from this mixture which is used as the natural binder to fix the broken stone pieces traditionally. It has been used in consolidation, restoration and conservation works of sculptures, carvings, panels, architectural members etc., since ages and is still in practice. But, due to the commercial reasons and easier availability, the artisans of Sukhuapda started using Araldite and Lapox instead of this traditional adhesive which is not long lasting and satisfactory.

Fig.6. Fermentation of natural ingredients in a stone trough

Fig.7. Indigenous adhesive paste for fixating stones

Challenges and Opportunities in Preserving Sukhuapada's Legacy

Despite its rich heritage, Sukhuapada faces several challenges. One of the most pressing issues is the declining number of young artisans willing to continue the tradition. Many young people are drawn to urban centres in search of better economic opportunities, leaving the craft in the hands of an ageing population. This has created a void for young, active and energetic artistic groups.

Another challenge is the lack of formal recognition and support for the artisans. While Sukhuapada's sculptures are highly valued in the market, the artisans often struggle to secure fair compensation for their work. This is compounded by the rising cost of materials and the competition from mass-produced alternatives. Lack of awareness amongst the young generation about their own history, tradition and legacy has its own disadvantages.

However, there are also opportunities for preserving Sukhuapada's legacy. Initiatives such as government grants, craft fairs, and academic studies can help raise awareness and provide financial support for the artisans. Additionally, collaborations with designers and architects can open new avenues for innovation while preserving the essence of the tradition (Dash, 2018).

Conclusion

The sculpting tradition of Sukhuapada, steeped in sustainability, spirituality, and community, represents more than an art form—it is a cultural heritage of profound significance. However, this legacy faces existential challenges due to the growing dominance of modern sculptural workshops in cities like Bhubaneswar. The easy accessibility of stones and modern machinery has shifted stone cutting and sculpting practices away from traditional methods, threatening the indigenous knowledge systems that have thrived for centuries.

Although initiatives like the government's crafts village scheme offer hope, they are not sufficient to reverse the decline of these traditional practices. What is needed is a comprehensive vision that integrates economic support, education, and global promotion of these heritage crafts. By recognising the historical and cultural value of Sukhuapada's artistry, and by bridging the gap between tradition and modernity, we can ensure that these ancient techniques not only survive but flourish.

This preservation effort is not merely about safeguarding a craft; it is about upholding a way of life that emphasises ecological wisdom, spiritual depth, and communal harmony. It is our collective responsibility to revive and promote this invaluable legacy, ensuring it continues to inspire the world and enrich the lives of future generations.

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